

CURRICULUM VITAE

1970

ANDREW GEORGE WILLIAMSON

HOME ADDRESS: Ollaberry,
Grimms Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks,
ENGLAND.

CURRENT ADDRESS: The British Institute of Persian Studies,
P.O. Box 2617,
Teheran,
IRAN.

BORN: 18/12/1945. AGE: 24 years.

EDUCATION: Rugby School, Rugby, Warwickshire. 1959-1963.
Certificate in Spanish Language and Civilization, 1964.
Madrid University.
Pembroke College, Oxford University. 1964-1967.
2nd Class Honours Degree in Modern History. 1967.
Specialization-Later Roman and Byzantine History
Research Student at Pembroke College, Oxford. From 1967.

LANGUAGES: Spanish-very good. German-poor.
Portuguese-adequate. Persian-fair.
Latin-good. Arabic-very poor.
French-good.

FELLOWSHIPS & GRANTS: Department of Education and Science Major State
Studentship. 1967-1969. Renewed 1969-1970.
Fellow of The British Institute of Persian
Studies. 1968-1969. Renewed 1969-1970.
Honourary Fellow of The British Institute of
Persian Studies. 1970-1971.
Grantee of The Wainwright Fund for Near Eastern
Archaeology of The University of Oxford.
1970-1971. For archaeological survey in
Southern Iran.
Grantee of The Stein-Arnold Fund of The British
Academy. 1969. For excavation at Sirjan.
Grantee of The Meyerstein Research Fund of The
University of Oxford. 1969. For excavation
at Sirjan.
Grantee of The Siraf Fund of The British Institute
of Persian Studies. 1969. For excavation
at Sirjan.

- PUBLICATIONS: "Islamic Trade Routes in Southern Iran", Iran VIII, 1970, pp. 202-203.
- "Excavations at Sirjan", Iran IX, 1971, in press.
- "Excavations at Tepe Dasht-i Deh", Iran IX, 1971, in press.
- "Excavations at Sirjan", full excavation report in preparation for Iran X, 1972.
- "Excavations at Tepe Dasht-i Deh", full excavation report in preparation for The Papers of the Peabody Museum, Harvard University.
- Introducing Persian Pottery of the Islamic Period, Asia Institute Publications, in preparation.
- with Martha Prickett, "Survey on the Persian Gulf Coast", Iran IX, 1971, in press.

EXCAVATION EXPERIENCE: Warren Percy. Deserted Mediaeval Village. 1965.
 Rainsborough Hill Fort. Iron Age and Roman. 1965.
 Oxford Castle. Saxon and Mediaeval. 1965.
 Cirencester. Saxon Minster. 1966.
 Southampton. Mediaeval Town. 1966.
 Nush-i Jan, Iran. Median and Parthian. 1967.
 Qumis, Iran. Parthian and Islamic. 1967.
 Siraf, Iran. Islamic. 1967-1968.
 1968-1969.

EXCAVATIONS DIRECTED: Sirjan, Iran. Islamic. 1970.
 Tepe Dasht-i Deh, Iran. Islamic. 1970.
 (as part of the Harvard Iran Expedition to Tepe Yahya).

TRAVEL IN ISLAMIC COUNTRIES 1964-1970: Spain. Iraq.
 Morrocco. Iran.
 Algeria. Pakistan.
 Turkey. Afghanistan.